

Carl Fredricksen: shaping a grumpy

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Abstract

The audience's empathy by the animated film (feature-length) UP (2009) is verified by its commercial and critical success and by the two Oscar awards received. Based on the Visual Sense and using the animated film UP as a research corpus, the current work aims to investigate the using of shapes on character design proceeding. To investigate this method, it was analyzed the protagonist's visual development at the film's beginning: Carl Fredricksen a calm, grouchy and sad old man. Besides the animated film, the *corpus* was also be composed by The Art of Up (2009), written by Tim Hauser, one of the film's directors. In this book, the concept arts developed for the animated film by his production team are presented and described in detail. The theoretical framework was composed by authors such as Arnheim (2011), Dondis (1997), Bancroft (2006) and Nakata & Silva (2013).

Keywords: Character Design, UP, Basic Shapes, Animation, Carl Fredricksen

Introduction

The main purpose for this article is to describe the basic shapes use in character design; how they influence the production of meanings among the spectator audience. Secondly, contribute to ensuring that the Character Design proceeding is not limited to just drawing techniques. Technique is important but it is a tool to be used together with other resources in the creation process. Understanding the construction of a character means advancing within the diegesis and the created universe, its rules, limitations, and objectives.

According to Visual Perception theories, it is known that basic geometric shapes generate meanings. However, a question arises in character design: to what extent shape using technique contributes, in a strategic manner, to the construction and reinforcement of meanings to be intended generated?

To evaluate this issue on character design, a corpus was chosen that shows its intentional and strategic nature. The selected corpus is composed by two objects: the feature-length animated film UP (2009), produced by Disney Pixar Studios; and the book The Art of Up (2009), which is about the process of artistic elaboration for the film. It was written by the directors and contains testimonies from the production team.

As a corpus, the prologue of the animated film is analyzed, it is one of the greatest emotional charge sequences and it contains the best case to be studied. It will help in this research investigation proposal: to analyze the visual construction of a character as a reinforcement of its personality audiences can understand.

Character Design: concoction

The word “design” for *praxis* and regular proceedings (character design, background design, assets design etc.) may mean to project. Specifically, character design manages to exemplify well the concept of designing factors embedded in the word design, highlighting the purposeful intention behind creating images. When designing a character, it is necessary to be aware of producing meaning for the target audience. In this regard, Seegmiller (2008, as mentioned by NAKATA; SILVA, 2013, p. 59) describes design as able to bring to surface the audience’s beliefs, expectations, and reactions related to the character’s formal aspects, appearance, and subjective traits.

For the character to be well-designed and efficient, some aspects must be verified, which were listed based on the study of Tom Bancroft, who worked at the Disney animation companies for twelve years for some of their famous productions. Bancroft established in his book Creating Characters with personality (2006) aspects for developing characters, creating a parameterization, throughout its publication, so that the character design activity can be successful in producing meaning in the audience-spectator. We will also walk through the theory from Diane S. Berry and Leslie Zebrowitz McArthur’s article “Perceiving Character in Faces: The Impact of Age-Related

Craniofacial Changes on Social Perception” (1986), which ponders how people’s perception is directly related to facial appearance.

It is important to say that this parameterization establishes aspects and/or steps that do not necessarily need to happen separately. They can, and often will, happen at the same time. Designers can use these parameters as the character development is in progress. These are the aspects: shape, scale, variation, silhouette, pose and emotion, color palette and style.

Therefore, the activity of designing a character is a practice that requires attention to previously outlined objectives (the director's and author's objectives in the briefing) and care when choosing visual resources that can reinforce a personality.

For this article, we will limit ourselves to study the basic shapes that make up the design (visual structures) on Carl Fredricksen, protagonist of the animated feature film UP (2009) in four moments in his life: childhood, early adulthood, maturity, and old age.

Character design and Visual Perception

Character design practices are based on visual perception. Visual Perception must be connected to the creation process if success is in the goals. Any character project follows a specific purpose that will rely on the way we perceive the visual constructions in the appearance of the characters. As Berry and McArthur (1986, p. 4) said "When asked to describe what someone is like, we begin by describing their appearance, and when asked why we want to get to know someone we cite aspects of their appearance." In this project, visual elaboration is the vehicle for visual perception guides its entire structure. Dondis (1997, p.30) explain that while creating visual messages, meaning is shared by common mechanisms of perception, resulting in choices of color, tones, textures, and dimensions. Each one carrying certain meanings.

There is no difference for character design: the objective set by the director and the author needs to be achieved according to their understanding of the audience. And the success in achieving such is directly related to the techniques, concepts, and shapes to be used in the visual structure.

A connection can be established between the first law of visual perception with the first character design process: creation of basic shapes. According to Arnheim (2011, p. 47), the first

law of visual perception claims that any pattern of stimulus shall be simply perceived in accordance with the given conditions.

In other words, the visual configurations used in the characters design tend to be interpreted in the simplest way possible. Therefore, the first practice of character design is to design basic shapes. Thus, each character starts from the premise of a primary geometric shape. It commonly starts by the head and face: “To summarize, it appears that our perception of people's character is strongly tied to their facial appearance” (BERRY; MCARTHUR, 1986, p. 6).

Figure 01 – Initial practice on *character design*. Basic shapes.

Note: BANCROFT, 2006.

From this starting point, the character designer uses the concepts of visual perception to build the character visual style and consequently their personality. Remembering that the entire visual construction elaborated in this practice follows the objectives previously specified by the film's direction.

Back to the concept of simplicity proposed by the laws of visual perception, Arnheim (2011, p. 47) define simplicity as a subjective experience and the observer's judgement due to the ability in remembering and imaging it.

When continuing to build the character's visual structure, the practice continues to apply basic shapes and define what in visual perception is understood as shape. To define this aspect, Arnheim (2011, p. 89) states that shape is a content's visible configuration.

Figure 02 – The following process in *character design*, shape definition

Note: BANCROFT, 2006, l. 445.

As previously mentioned, Bancroft (2006) pointed out that a character's design conveys meaning even before the character speaks or does anything. With this statement, it is understood that different shapes evoke different meanings.

According to Dondis (1997, p. 58) each basic shape has their own specific meaning. Some of the latter by association, some by arbitrary bond, and others by psychological and physiological perceptions.

The meaning of Dondis' assertion can be seen in Bancroft's (2016) words, even more specifically: "These basic shapes will give you the visual cues you need to describe your characters. They become the foundation for your characters' personality traits and overall attitudes" (p. 489). And continues: "Circles - evoke appealing, good characters and are typically used to connote cute, cuddly, friendly types. Consider Santa Claus, or endearing, fuzzy animals" Bancroft (2016, l. 489).

Thus, if the character has circular shapes in its design, there is a high probability that it will be interpreted as a good-natured and friendly figure. From this perspective, we can refer to Baymax, one of the protagonists of the animated film *Big Hero 6* (2014), who is a soft-spoken and calm inflatable robot, created to take care of people and has a first aid kit, wound scanners, among other gadgets.

Figure 03 – Baymax, *Big Hero 6* (2014)

Note: Traced by the authors (Jan 2024)

If we look at the shapes used in Baymax's design, we will notice many circular and rounded shapes. Visual perception, through shapes, explains why this sense of tranquility is obtained. The simplicity of the circular shape guarantees its characteristic. Dondis (1997) and Arnheim (2011, p. 165) claim the circle to be the simplest shape.

Figure 4 – Equilibrium in a circular shape

Note: (DONDIS, 1997)

With this thought in mind, Dondis (1997, p. 58) also states that the circle is associated with infinity, warmth, and protection.

A circle creates a sense of tranquility and is not very provocative. It's a balanced and simple structure that leaves no room for aggressive and provocative lines.

Following the explanation of the meanings of different shapes and their different meanings, we then moved to quadrangular shapes. In Bancroft's opinion (2006, l. 507), squares “usually depict characters who are dependable or solid (...). Next time you're out at a club, check out the bouncer, one big old square. The design of superheroes often relies on square shapes”.

Square shapes are regular shapes made up of four points connected by lines that do not intersect, they continue end to end. There are four corners aligned and balanced by tension, covering a certain area in a sober and stable way, forming a system of balance, as if four forces pulled equally in four directions from opposite pairs.

As stated by Arnheim (2011, p.6), forces find equilibrium in the center of a square, contrary to the circle which does not favor any direction. Dondis (1997, p. 58) corroborates it with similar understanding of a square.

Disney’s character Ralph (*Wreck it Ralph*, 2012) is an example of a predominantly square-shaped design.

Figure 05 – Ralph, *Wreck it Ralph* (2012)

Note: Traced by the authors (Jan 2024)

On the other hand, triangles “easily lend themselves to more sinister, suspicious types and usually represent the bad guy or villain in character designs” (BANCROFT, 2006, 513).

Triangular shapes mostly derive from diagonal lines and have the character of obliquity.

Arnheim (2011, p. 177) explains that obliquity is always perceived as a deviation, hence its dynamic character, and can also be a vital differentiator in relation to static compositions. He refers to diagonal lines rather than horizontal and vertical lines, which would denote a deviation in the path between a vertical and a horizontal point.

Tillman (2011, p. 70) reflects about the matter: “What do you think the triangle is trying to convey? Again, a triangle conveys the following: Action, Aggression, Energy, Sneakiness, Conflict and Tension”. In this sense, Dondis (1997, p. 58) associates triangles with action, conflict

and tension, reasons why this shape can be associated with villains, such as Hades (Figure 06), a character from the animated film *Hercules* (1997), produced by Disney. Hades has several triangular shapes: nose, face shape, teeth, ears, and fingertips:

Figure 06 - Hades, *Hercules* (1997)

Note: Traced by the authors (Jan 2024)

Shaping grumpiness

The animated feature *Up* tells the story of Carl Fredricksen, a 78-year-old grumpy and bad-tempered balloon salesman who, after having his life turned upside down after his wife's passing, finds himself in a difficult situation: his house, one of the few reminders of his beloved one, is the target of harassment from buyers who want to demolish it to transform the neighborhood into a shopping mall complex. In an impulsive decision, Carl ties countless balloons to his house and runs away to take it to South America, on a trip that was his and his late wife childhood dream. Along the way, Carl discovers that he is not alone. Russell, an 8-year-old Boy Scout, was on his porch at that time. The duo travels and overcomes several setbacks along the way.

The film shows how the beautiful friendship that arises between Carl and Russell promotes changes in the grumpy old man.

The book *The Art of UP* (2009) is a publication written by Tim Hauser, showing details of how the animation was designed, bringing in its content images from visual studies and testimonies from production members and the director, which reveals the intentions of these studies for the film's result.

The film's prologue tells the life story of the protagonist, clarifying what motivated him to become surly and lonely, an important aspect for the film's entire narrative. The choice of this sequence is justified because it is in it that the Carl's personality is established by counting four distinguished moments: childhood, early adulthood, maturity, and old age. And for each moment of his life, there are basic shapes that corroborates the construction of his personality and how it is aimed at the audience's perception. Like Berry and McArthur (1986, p.4) say: "people's facial appearances clearly influence our impressions of their psychological qualities [...]".

Next, this paper shows how these visual constructions are applied to reinforce and influence meanings.

Figure 07 – Four distinguished moments of Carl's life

Note: Animation Screenshot compilation traced by the authors

Moment 1, Carl as a child

The design aims to show the life of a shy, yet dreamy and adventurous child.

Figure 08 – Child Carl

Note: Animation screenshot compilation traced by the authors

The basic shape for structuring child Carl design is the circle. As mentioned, the circular shape is used to create cute, kind, and friendly characters. Bancroft (2006, p. 500) points out that: “Circles – evoke appealing, good characters and are typically used to connote cute, cuddly, friendly types. Consider Santa Claus, or endearing, fuzzy animals”. Dondis (1997, p. 58) also states that the circle is associated with infinity, warmth, and protection.

Moment 2, Carl’s early adulthood

Figure 09 - Carl Fredricksen early adulthood

Note: Animation Screenshot compilation traced by the authors

At this moment, the audience meets Carl in his youth, when he marries Ellie. It is worth noting that, when the character grows older, some physical characteristics are maintained, so that he is cognizable. In this case, we see Carl still with his eyes a very strong shade of blue, his hair, his topknot, and his behavior more restrained. For this phase of life, the character's design was structured with rectangles and squares, but with a peculiarity: they are rectangular shapes with rounded corners.

It is known, as previously reported in the protagonist's childhood phase, that circular shapes bring sympathy and tranquility. These characteristics were mixed with quadrangular shapes with firmer structuring, sobriety, and stability. This mixture demonstrates a transition, which goes from the circle to the square.

Moment 3, mature Carl

It is the shortest phase narrated in the animation's prologue, acting as a seal of continuity of the couple's joyful and happy moments in life. As an animation resource, repetitions were used to demonstrate time passing, but this does not prevent the character from being analyzed at least in most of its aspects. In his design, the square shapes remain as they were in youth, with the mix of rigidity of rectangular shapes and the fluidity and tranquility of circular shapes being preserved. His face, the design of his chest and the lines of his shoulders are rectangular with rounded corners.

Figure 10 – Mature Carl Fredricksen

Note: Animation Screenshot compilation made by the authors

Moment 4, aged Carl Fredricksen

At this moment, he is 78 years old, and his appearance and posture are very different from the previous three. He appears to be grumpy, with few friends, which contrasts with his other three moments, in which he was portrayed as a happy and lively character. This austere

countenance is a consequence of an event that occurred between moments three and four: the passing of the love of his life, his wife, Ellie.

Figure 11 - Carl Fredricksen, old aged

Note: Animation Screenshot compilation traced by the authors

The basic shapes used for Carl's design were square shapes, which can be seen in his face and expression lines. There is a repetition of square shapes, acting as reinforcement in the concepts of boredom and anger. His overall design structures are all square with very little corner rounding.

It is notable that it was a progression of the shapes that made up the protagonist's design, through a path followed by them, a logic that reveals the construction of the character's personality in the prologue. In the book *The Art of UP* (2009), there is also a study that demonstrates this evolution.

Figure 12 – Carl's character design studies

Note: HAUSER, 2009

The Figure above shows the study of how Carl's shapes should evolve over time. It is normal to be phases in the character's life that are not portrayed within the animation itself. However, studies must exist, as the stages of life need to be listed to support the creation process and give depth to the character. In the study. As the character ages, his features become squarer and wider. In practice, for the construction of design, this evolution reveals a personality that will stop being happy and cheerful, and become sad and boring as saw in previous visual perception theory.

Conclusion: the adventure is out there

To finish off the elaboration of Carl's design in his four moments of life, it is necessary to notice some details, noticing that some basic shapes are persistent. The first, obviously, is that the character needs to be recognized throughout his life: some characteristics are maintained in his design precisely so that his essence is not lost. The second, and more subjective: is the reason for trying to retrieve and reinforce some meanings. The persistence in Carl's design is the circular shapes.

In his childhood, circular shapes were used to their fullest extent. The circles are even present in the details of his clothes, as well as his eyes and nose. From early adulthood, squares took place, but were always influenced by circular shapes in their corners. Eyes and nose are still circular. And, more precisely at an advanced age, Carl's design, which leaves the surly characteristic of its square shapes well established, maintains the circular nose, which only increases in size as the years goes by. Other circular shapes are also added to his design, such as the tennis balls on his walking stick. These circular shapes could mean the rescue of some values that have remained throughout Carl's life, as a reminder of what once was and that there may still be something left in him, or even a spot of circular hope amid various annoyances. heavy and square.

The analysis carried out in this article manages to demonstrate how strategic the character design routine can be, proving that it cannot be reduced to just drawing techniques. With good character design, meanings can be awakened in the audience and contribute to more efficient and successful animation.

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